

Born's Rule and Classical Physics For a Single Particle and Superposition in Classical Probability

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In this note we try to argue that Born's rule and the notion of the wavefunction follow from classical considerations of spatial probability which represent a static and not dynamic scenario. In classical physics, the probability weight for any momentum or velocity at x is a constant. In other words, this spatial probability does not distinguish between momenta which is an issue if one deals with impulse hits. As a result, a measure called pressure is introduced which multiplies a value proportional to impulse, namely p (momentum), by velocity which is a flux. It is velocity which distinguishes between particles with different v , even though each has the same probability weight at each x point (for constant velocity). This works well if one has multiple particles.

There exist, however, cases focusing on one kind of particle moving in a steady stream (photon) which may have different momentum values (and speed values) in different regions of space, as in a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. In such a case, the incident and refracted photon moves in the same direction and it would be good to have a kind of continuous x,p probability. The usual x probability weight is a constant dx/L (where L is length) for each p (p incident and p reflected), but this is not the full physical picture because there are different momenta, hence different impulses. This same situation seems to also apply to free quantum particles in space which have different momentum values. It seems there should be a probability based on p and x which may be used for interactions which differs from the constant value which applies for the constant x weight probability which does not distinguish between one p value and another.

Given that spatial probability $P(p,x)dx = dx/L$ has no p dependence, it is static. (We use p instead of v because we are interested in impulses of a single particle.) We suggest that one remove p dependence by having a product probability $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)P_{\text{special}}(-p,x) = P(p,x) = 1/L$ ((1)). In other words, bypassing pressure considerations which introduce a velocity factor to account for different fluxes, we suggest that a single one directional stream (one dimensional photon reflection/refraction or free quantum particles) cannot use v as distinguishing variable. Instead, one requires two associated probabilities, as suggested by ((1)). This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a periodic solution, which is problematic because it is complex. If, however, one has a bound state, and one considers energy conservation, one may take an average of p and $-p$ because they represent the same kinetic energy. The issue, we suggest, is that if one does not want to use velocity as a distinguisher of different momenta (as in the case of pressure), but wants to only use probability considerations for a single particle, then this leads to two probabilities ((1)), one associated with spatial weights and the other with momentum weights, with a specific connection between the two. This connection, we argue, leads to the Born Rule.

We note that for a single particle bound state, in order to create an average kinetic energy at x , needed for energy conservation, one must average over all distinct p values at a single point x . This is equivalent to having many values of one parameter (p) apply to a single value of a second parameter (x). (1) calls this superposition and argues that Born's Rule follows from using classical probability together with superposition. A matrix is created using an outer product. We use the example, $a^*(p_i)a(p_j) \exp(-ip_i x) \exp(ip_j x)$ and note that (1)'s ideas of superposition are consistent with this picture. We stress that the whole idea of having many p values map to one x value, however, follows from the inadequacy of the static probability $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ describing a dynamic situation in x,p . As a result, a "square root" probability is required, because its product with its complex conjugate yields the static probability value.

Quantum Free Particle and Classical Physics

Classical physics indicates that a particle with constant momentum, and hence constant velocity, has a constant weight probability at each x because the particle spends the same amount of time in

each equally spaced dx region. Given a specific p (corresponding to a specific v), this probability is:

$$P(x,p) dx = P(x,p/m=v) dx = dx/L \quad ((2))$$

As a result, this probability is completely independent of p (and hence v). If one thinks of a single particle with constant p , it represents an impulse of $2p$ if it reflects with $-p$. The question is: What is the spatial probability for such an impulse? ((2)) suggests the same spatial probability for all p , but this cannot be used in an impulse problem as different p values represent different impulses. Furthermore, one cannot multiply $2p$ by velocity, as one does in a classical gas, because there is only one particle. The same holds for a photon which undergoes one dimensional reflection/refraction.

Why does one need a probability density based on p and x ? Given that $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$ describes probability in space and that potentials are also described in space, such as a 2-slit apparatus which has slit widths of known length, a separation of known length and a center of mass position, there should also exist a probabilistic description for x and p to describe impulse interactions. $P(x,p)$ does not suffice because it treats different p values in the same way, i.e. is essentially a static picture. This leads to a major issue, because it suggests two probabilities are needed. The probability $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ is a relative type of probability because it describes relative weightings of dx units. It holds for p and $-p$ as well as for any p magnitude value. In a problem with impulses, one requires an actual x,p probability, not a relative one which can differentiate between p and $-p$ and between different p magnitude values.

Formally, one may see $P(x,p)dx$ defined in the literature as the amount of time dt spent in each dx region, where each dx has a constant length. dt is then $dx/(\text{magnitude } v)$. This unnormalized value is different for different v values even if p is the same and renders the same impulse, which is a problem. Furthermore, normalization removes any information about v , i.e. one has dx/L . In other words, $P(x,p)$ removes all dynamics of the problem for a constant v, p . $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ equally describes one static particle in each dx as it does constant motion, p . In fact, it is this equivalence with a static scenario which allows one to find a $P_{\text{special}}(x,p)$ because one may focus on p (impulse) and argue that:

$$P_{\text{special}}(x,p) P_{\text{special}}(x,-p) = \text{static picture so} = dx/L \quad ((3))$$

This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution. We argue that this result follows from purely classical considerations. The classical $P(x,p)$ is a static probability which yields only relative dynamic information. If such a probability exists and is used, there should be one which includes dynamics, we argue. The fact that the two map into each other shows that they are not completely independent, which one would expect.

Issues with $\exp(ipx)$

$\exp(ipx)$ may be normalized, but this does not change the fact that it is complex which seems like a problem. A complex probability, however, can lead to real p and $pp/2m$ average values through:

$$p(x) = p \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) \text{ and } p(x)p(x)/2m \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

These lead to the classical values of p and $pp/2m$ which could have been obtained using dx/L . As a result, why should one use $\exp(ipx)$? We argue that the reason one needs a dynamic probability with explicit dependence on p and x is to solve problems involving potentials in space, such as a two-slit interference pattern which may establish a steady stream result. dx/L is the same for p and $-p$, and so cannot be used, as one expects different results for each. The consequences, however, are great because $\exp(ipx)$ leads to interference/diffraction patterns.

A second argument for $\exp(ipx)$ is the one dimensional reflection/refraction of a photon. One cannot use dx/L to describe the incident and refracted photons dynamically as it is a relative probability. It has the same value for the incident and refracted photon (the reflected one as well), which does not describe the physics of the problem. These arguments, we suggest, are purely classical.

$\exp(ipx)$ suggests a characteristic length, \hbar/p , for a constant p . This seems to lead to issues when comparing with Newtonian mechanics which suggests a constant p only exists in a dx region and changes from one to another according to a potential $V(x)$. dx approaching 0, however, is an idealization. If p is sufficiently large, then \hbar/p fits in dx in all cases. What if \hbar/p , however, is comparable with the length of the physical system and yet there is still a $V(x)$? One must have energy conservation, on average, and so consider an average kinetic energy using $\exp(ipx)$'s as a probability weighting. $\exp(ipx)$ was introduced, however, for exactly this purpose, to deal with impulse or energy considerations.

Wavefunctions and Matrices

As a result, one may consider a probabilistic OR situation for a potential $V(x)$ i.e.

$$P_{\text{special}} = W(x) \text{ (called a wavefunction)} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((4a))$$

This leads to an average kinetic energy of:

$$(\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)) \quad ((4b))$$

Given that $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx)$ is the recipe to freeze out motion to find a static spatial x distribution, this same process should be applied to ((4)), as we have argued in previous notes. This leads to:

$$\text{spatial static density} = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((5))$$

This may be thought of in terms of a related matrix with components:

$$a^*(p_i)a(p_j) \exp(-i p_i x) \exp(i p_j x) \quad ((5))$$

If one integrates each matrix element over dx , then only diagonal entries remain, and these are $a^*(p_i)a(p_i)$ (no sum and i represents the i th diagonal element). If the Trace is normalized to 1, then it represents a sum of free particle static probabilities for given p_i values, which may be interpreted as the probability to find a p_i somewhere within the x range of integration from minus to plus infinite.

((5)) is also the outer product of the vector $a(p_i)\exp(i p_i x)$ with itself as argued in (1). In other words, to create a static density at x , one may have any p_i present. In other words, many p_i values are associated with the same x point. We still maintain that only classical arguments have been used so far.

We point out that ((5)) is consistent with the theory of (1) which we describe in the next section.

Theory of the Superposition of Probability

(1) suggests that Born's Rule follows from classical probability theory if one allows for superposition. In other words, multiple classical properties of one type, may be associated with a single property probability of a different type. For example, (1) considers white and black heart, diamond and clover shapes. The two properties are shape and colour. If one wishes to know a

probability associated with a colour, many shapes map to this colour. (1) calls this superposition and creates an outer product leading to a matrix identical to ((5)) in form. In fact, ((5)) uses superposition because many momentum values p_i (one property) are associated with another single property, x . (1) argues that Born's Rule follows directly from classical probability if one allows for such a superposition and creates matrices like ((5)).

We argue that Born's Rule is linked to $W^*(x)W(x)$, which in turn is a way to take the dynamic probability $W(x)$ (which involves superposition because many p values contribute to the single point x), and convert it into a static probability. We have argued throughout that we have been using classical reasoning and suggest that the freezing out of dynamics using $W^*(x)W(x)$ is equivalent to the notion of superposition applied to classical probability theory as described in (1).

We argue that superposition appears in the first place because the classical probability $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ is a static probability and so one is forced to find a dynamic one dependent on x and p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ for a constant p is a relative type of probability which may as well describe a static situation of one particle in each dx as it is the same for any p . Given that one uses probability in space and there exist potentials, like 2-slit ones with exact x positions, we suggest there should also exist a special probability in x,p (as p is used for impulse). Such a probability could be used to show how a particle with a constant p interacts with a 2-slit apparatus etc. whereas $P(x,p)$ cannot as it is the same for p and $-p$ (and any other p). We suggest that such an interaction may be seen as a steady state scenario and so such a P special should exist. Given that $P(x,p)$ is equivalent to a static probability, we suggest that: $P_{\text{special}}(p,x) P_{\text{special}}(-p,x) = P(x,p) = 1/L$ where L is length. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution.

If one wishes to use energy conservation for a single particle bound state with $V(x)$, one cannot associate a constant p with a dx , as in Newtonian theory, unless \hbar/p fits within dx . As a result, one is forced to average over many p at each x point i.e. $KE_{\text{average}} = (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx))$. This suggests that many values of one type of property, namely p , apply to a single point x of a different property. We also suggest that our arguments are purely classical.

(1) suggests that Born's Rule (i.e. quantum mechanics) follows directly from classical probability theory if one introduces the idea of superposition. Superposition is the idea that many values of one property contribute to a single value of another property, like the p, x example given above. (1) creates a matrix using an outer product, just like ((5)) above, i.e. $a^*(p_i)a(p_j) \exp(-i p_i x) \exp(ip_j x)$ and argues that one may obtain Born's rule and quantum mechanics using ideas from classical probability together with superposition.

We argue that classical probabilities apply and that superposition arises because $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ is a static probability which does not distinguish between p values. In an attempt to find a dynamic probability which leads to $P(x,p)$ when one freezes out motion ($P_{\text{special}}(p,x)P_{\text{special}}(-p,x) = P(p,x)$) which may be used for problems with potentials, like 2-slit potentials, one obtains the form $\exp(ipx)$. This forces one to create an average kinetic using many distinct p values (superposition) at a fixed x point. Momentum p represents one property and x another and many values of one property apply to one value of a different property, which is the superposition of (1).

Thus, given a static probability $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$, one is forced to find a corresponding special dynamic probability depending on p and x . This means that an average function of p at x depends on many values of p or one uses superposition. The recipe for converting the superposition expression to a static probability is to multiply by its complex conjugate, which is directly linked to the Born Rule when one integrates over x . In the case of the Born Rule, one may explicitly use: $\int dx W^*(x)V(x)W(x)$.

References

1. Ellerman, D. Where does the Born Rule Come From? Superposition. (2023)
[\[2310.04188v3\] Where does the Born Rule come from? Superposition \(arxiv.org\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.04188v3)

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